

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA CELEBRITY ENDORSEMENT ON CONSUMER PATRONAGE OF *INDOMIE* NOODLES

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ABSTRACT

Social media celebrity endorsement has a great influence on the buying decisions of people. It has a vast ability to attract attention, create interest, and build trust in products or services. Social media celebrity endorsement tends to play an increasingly vital role in shaping brand image and increasing customer loyalty. It plays vital roles in marketing by boosting sales, spreading brand awareness, and connecting brands with wider audiences. This study explores the influence of social media celebrity endorsement on consumer patronage. The study examined the level of exposure, level of patronage, influence, and examined the challenges in accessing the advertisement of *Indomie Noodles*, following the endorsements by celebrities. The perception and source credibility theories were adopted for the study. Survey design was used for a population of 21,898, a total of three hundred and seventy-seven (377) sample size was drawn. Three hundred and seventy-seven (377) copies of questionnaire were administered and all were returned. The data collected were analyzed using tables, simple percentages and likert-scale. The study found out that respondents are highly influenced by social media celebrity endorsement on *Indomie Noodles* and it has a positive influence and it enhances consumer patronage. This study based on the findings therefore recommend that a use of qualitative methods is suggested to gain deeper insight on the influence of social media celebrity endorsed products on consumer patronage of *Indomie Noodles*.

Keywords: Communication, Advertising, Product, *Indomie* noodles, Celebrity endorsement, Consumer behaviour

Introduction

Celebrities are influential media personalities who hold a high social status and use public relations to maintain their image (Hu *et al*, 2017). They are often seen as role models, shaping public opinion, setting trends, and influencing buying decisions. Many people, especially young adults, admire celebrities and try to copy their lifestyles, believing that owning the same products will improve their social status (Boon & Lomore, 2021). This strong emotional connection makes celebrity-endorsed products more desirable to consumers. Studies show that people sometimes pay large amounts for items linked to their favorite celebrities, even if these products do not have extra value on their own (Newman & Bloom, 2014).

In recent years, social media has become a powerful tool for celebrity endorsements. With platforms like Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, and TikTok, celebrities can connect directly with their followers and promote brands in a personal way (Jin & Muqaddam, 2019; Emetumah *et al.*, 2022). Social media celebrity endorsements work because fans trust their favorite influencers and believe their recommendations are genuine. Unlike traditional advertising, where endorsements are often scripted, social

media allows for more interactive and engaging promotions. This has made it easier for businesses to use celebrities as brand ambassadors to attract consumers and boost sales (Lou & Yuan, 2019).

There are three key factors that determine the success of a celebrity endorsement. The first is celebrity fit, which refers to how well a celebrity matches the brand's image and values (Muda *et al*, 2017). The second is celebrity credibility, which is based on the trustworthiness and honesty of the celebrity (Schimmelpfennig & Hollensen, 2016). Lastly, celebrity expertise refers to how much knowledge or experience the celebrity has with the product they are endorsing (Lou & Yuan, 2019). Although many studies have explored these factors, few have examined how they work together to influence consumer buying behavior, especially in Nigeria.

In Nigeria, celebrity endorsements play a major role in influencing consumer behavior, especially in industries such as consumer goods. *Indomie Noodles* has successfully used social media influencers and celebrities to strengthen brand loyalty and attract young consumers (Ibrahim & Akintunde, 2019).

Celebrity endorsement is a marketing strategy in which well-known personalities are employed to promote a product, service, or brand. The effectiveness of celebrity endorsements is rooted in the psychological association that consumers develop between the endorser and the endorsed product (Erdogan, 2019). The success of this strategy is determined by three key dimensions: celebrity fit, celebrity credibility, and celebrity expertise. Celebrity fit refers to the alignment between the celebrity's persona and the brand's identity, ensuring authenticity and relatability.

Celebrity credibility pertains to the perceived trustworthiness and sincerity of the endorser, which influences consumer confidence in the brand. Celebrity expertise, on the other hand, signifies the level of knowledge or experience that a celebrity possesses in relation to the endorsed product category (Adeyanju & Olusola, 2021). These elements play a crucial role in shaping consumer attitudes toward brands, particularly in the context of social media advertising, where influencers and brand ambassadors wield significant power.

The study aims to fill the knowledge gap by analysing the impact of social media celebrity endorsements on consumer patronage, by focusing on the product category: *Indomie noodles*, a widely consumed food product. The study will gather opinions from students at Prince Abubakar Audu University (PAAU), Anyigba, since young adults are prone to have a celebrity figure they admire and are heavily influenced by, because celebrities play a significant role in shaping consumer behavior (Oyeleke & Olatunji, 2020).

The influence of celebrity endorsements in contemporary marketing has significantly shaped consumer purchasing behavior, particularly in the digital age. While extensive research has validated the impact of celebrity endorsements in driving brand visibility and consumer engagement, there remains a critical gap in understanding how this strategy differentially impacts various product categories. The effectiveness of social media celebrity endorsements in stimulating consumer patronage is often contingent upon factors such as product type, consumer perception, and brand credibility.

This study interrogates the extent to which social media celebrity endorsements influence consumer patronage by using *Indomie Noodles*, a widely consumed household brand. Given the differences in consumer motivation for purchasing consumables, it remains uncertain whether the persuasive power of celebrity endorsements is potent for the product category. As consumer goods like *Indomie Noodles* uses celebrity appeal to enhance emotional connectivity and impulse buying, the absence of empirical studies examining the effectiveness in the Nigerian market underscores the need for a rigorous analysis.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

- 1) Examine the exposure to *Indomie Noodles* advertisement.
- 2) Ascertain the level of patronage of *Indomie Noodles* by customers after being exposed to the adverts by celebrities.
- 3) Determine the levels of influence of the celebrity on the patronage of *Indomie Noodles* and by customers.
- 4) Examine the challenges in accessing the advertisement of *Indomie Noodles*, following the endorsements by celebrities.

Theoretical Framework

The Theory adopted for this study is the perception theory. Perception Theory was first introduced in the field of psychology in the early 20th century by Gestalt psychologists, but it became more formally applied to marketing and consumer behavior in the 1950s and 1960s. The theory explains how individuals make sense of the information they receive through their senses what they see, hear, feel, or experience.

In advertising and marketing, Perception Theory helps to understand how consumers notice, interpret, and respond to promotional messages and brand communication (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2016). Perception is not just about seeing or hearing something it involves how a person understands and makes meaning from the message. Two people can see the same advertisement and have very different opinions about it based on their background, emotions, personal needs, and previous experiences.

This is why perception is considered subjective. Consumers first notice an advert, then pay attention to its message, and finally interpret it based on what they already know or feel. What they believe about the product is formed through this process. This theory is important to advertising because it helps marketers understand that consumers do not always react to adverts in the same way. An advert that works for one group of people may not work for another group. Marketers must therefore try to understand the target audience's values, culture, and interests when designing their messages (Kotler & Armstrong, 2018).

In Nigerian, the role of perception in advertising is very visible. Scholars such as Olayinka and Aminu (2019) found that the way people perceive a celebrity endorser plays a major role in their response to the product. If the audience sees the celebrity as trustworthy, stylish, and relevant, they are more likely to see the product in a positive light. But if the celebrity is involved in scandals or seems insincere, people may develop a negative attitude towards the brand being endorsed.

Ezenwa and Ohakwe (2020) also confirmed that in Nigeria, consumers' perception of the celebrity strongly influences their trust in the product. The emotional connection people have with celebrities helps shape how they feel about the products those celebrities promote. An example of this can be seen with the *Indomie Noodles* brand in Nigeria.

The company has used popular figures like Don Jazzy, a well-loved music producer, and Teni, a talented singer, in their promotional campaigns. These celebrities are known for being relatable, and entertaining. Many young people in Nigeria admire them, and because of that, they associate *Indomie Noodles* with fun, quality, and trust. This positive perception makes consumers more likely to choose the product over others in the market.

Relevance of Perception Theory to the Study

Perception Theory is relevant to this study as it helps to explain how consumers form opinions about products that are endorsed by celebrities on social media. This theory gives insight into why some people are attracted to endorsed products, while others are not, even when they are seeing the same advert. Perception is a personal process.

What one person sees as a good advert may not appeal to another person. This difference is often based on individual background, personal needs, mood, or past experience (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2016). This makes the theory very useful in understanding the different ways young people in Nigeria respond to celebrity endorsements on platforms like Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok. When a celebrity shares a post promoting *Indomie Noodles*, the way fans perceive the celebrity and the product will influence whether or not they are interested in buying it.

This theory also helps in explaining why some advertising campaigns work well with certain groups of people and not with others. For instance, young people may relate more to celebrities who dress like them, speak like them, and share similar values. If a brand fails to connect with the audience's way of thinking, the product may not be accepted, no matter how famous the celebrity is. This is why marketers need to study their audience's culture, preferences, and expectations before choosing a celebrity for endorsement (Kotler & Armstrong, 2018).

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopts a survey research design. A survey is useful when a researcher wants to ask questions and understand what people think, feel, or do. To the study, a survey is the best method because it allows the researcher to collect answers from Prince Abubakar Audu University (PAAU), Anyigba students about how celebrity-endorsed products affect their buying habits. Using a survey makes it easier to reach a large number of people and get different opinions. It also helps to collect data in a short time and with less cost.

Population and Sampling

Thus, the population of this study consist of all students in Prince Abubakar Audu University Anyigba 2025. According to the Directorate of Academic Planning and Development (DAP&D) of Prince Abubakar Audu University, the population of the students in PAAU is, 21,898. This is the population of the study.

Using Kretcie and Morgan Sampling table, the sample size is 377. The sample was selected using multi-stage procedure involving stratified, simple random and accidental sampling techniques to select faculties of Social Science, Natural Sciences, Arts and Humanities and Management Sciences. Also, one department was selected randomly from each of the faculties.

These are Mass Communication, Physics, Public Administration and Theatre Arts. Accidental sampling was employed in administering copies of the questionnaire to respondents. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to respondents available and interested in partaking in the research. Thus, $377 \div 4 = 94$ copies for each department selected, while 95 copies were administered in Mass Communication, as a result of the population the respondents in the departments selected. These copies were dropped at the departmental general office where students visit for signing of course forms. The first 94 or 95 students filled the questionnaire.

Descriptive technique of data analysis was employed, using four-point Likert scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree.

To validate the instrument, face validity technique was used to validate the instrument. A copy of the questionnaire was presented to a Senior Lecturer in Mass Communication Department, Federal University, Lokoja. His observations and corrections were incorporated to validate the instrument. To test the reliability, 38 copies of the questionnaire were administered among students of Kogi State Polytechnic Lokoja. All the copies were retrieved and tested using Pearson’s *r*. The result shows a high positive correlation at 0.81, to make the instrument reliable.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The demographic description of respondents shows that more of the respondents were female, one hundred and ninety-six (196) representing (54.44%), while male respondents were lesser, one hundred and sixty-four, representing (45.55%). This implies that there were more female respondents than male. Furthermore, the age distribution of the respondents show that majority of the respondents were in the age bracket of 18-25 (80.27%). This implies that the respondents were mostly young adults who were not too old.

Finally, the table presents data on the distribution of the respondents according to marital status. Majority of the respondents (88.05%) are single, few are married (11.66%) and only (0.27%) are divorced, with no widow/widower. This supports the earlier age data, showing that most of the respondents are young and not yet married, this can influence their opinion.

Table 1: Level of exposure to the advertisement of *Indomie* noodles featuring celebrity endorsement

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
I often, see <i>Indomie Noodles</i> ads with celebrities.	127	150	40	43	360	3.40	1.22	Accepted
I see <i>Indomie</i> ads mostly on social media.	135	135	51	39	360	3.28	1.36	Accepted
I know some celebrities that promote <i>Indomie Noodles</i> on social media.	61	79	138	82	360	2.13	1.23	Rejected
I watch <i>Indomie</i> ads twice a month.	211	97	25	27	360	3.10	1.10	Accepted
I watch <i>Indomie</i> ads once in a while.	225	98	24	13	360	3.15	1.15	Accepted
Cumulative mean						3.02		Accepted

Table 1 shows an analysis on the level of exposure by respondents to the advertisements of *Indomie Noodles* featuring endorsement, using likert-scale format which shows the cumulative mean (x) of the 5 parameters used to test it. The first, second, fourth and fifth statements were accepted by the respondents at mean averages of indicating that the respondents have a high level of exposure to advertisement of *Indomie*

Noodles featuring celebrity, and tend to watch these ads occasionally, with some watching twice a month, and others once in a while. However, the respondents rejected the third proposition which shows that respondents do not know some celebrities that promote *Indomie Noodles* on social media.

Table 2: Extent to which exposure to celebrity endorsements influence the level of patronage of *Indomie* noodles by customers

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
Celebrity ads make me want to buy <i>Indomie Noodles</i> .	173	107	43	37	360	3.23	1.21	Accepted
I have bought <i>Indomie Noodles</i> after seeing a celebrity ads.	165	126	36	33	360	3.31	0.52	Accepted
I believe <i>Indomie Noodles</i> is a good product because of the celebrities in their ads.	193	132	25	20	360	3.14	0.23	Accepted
I remember the product easily after seeing a celebrity in the ads.	185	140	27	08	360	3.55	1.41	Accepted
I like <i>Indomie Noodles</i> more because my favorite celebrity promotes it.	168	138	31	23	360	4.31	1.31	Accepted
Cumulative mean						3.51		Accepted

Table 3 shows the analysis on the respondents that agree that celebrity endorsements influence how much respondents buy *Indomie Noodles*. The first, third, fourth and fifth statements were accepted, by an average mean, meaning that the respondents are exposed to celebrity endorsements to a large extent, which influences their level of patronage of *Indomie Noodles*, because their favorite celebrity appears in the endorsement. However, the second proportion was rejected by respondents, which states that some respondents haven't bought *Indomie Noodles* after seeing a celebrity ad. With a cumulative mean of 3.51 which is above the average of 3.00, it is clear that exposure to celebrity endorsement positively influences the level of patronage of *Indomie Noodles* among consumers.

Table 3: Extent to which involvement of celebrities in the advertisements influence customer patronage of *Indomie* noodles

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
Celebrities influence my decision to buy <i>Indomie Noodles</i> .	186	120	33	21	360	3.43	0.43	Accepted

I pay more attention to <i>Indomie Noodles</i> adverts when I see a celebrity.	176	160	21	03	360	3.91	1.14	Accepted
I feel the product is more trustworthy when endorsed by a celebrity.	40	75	102	143	360	2.28	1.04	Rejected
If the celebrity I like is in the advert, I am more likely to buy <i>Indomie Noodles</i> .	180	102	50	28	360	3.71	1.42	Accepted
Without a celebrity, I may not notice or remember the <i>Indomie Noodles</i> ads.	185	133	29	13	360	3.25	1.13	Accepted
Cumulative mean						3.32		Accepted

Table 4 shows the extent to which the involvement of celebrities in the advertisements influences consumer patronage of *Indomie Noodles*. The first, second, fourth and fifth proportions were accepted by the respondents, at mean average of 3.43, 3.91, 3.71, 3.25, while the third statement was rejected at the mean average of 2.28, this indicates that the involvement of celebrities in the advertisements influences the level consumer patronage of *Indomie Noodles*, but does not necessarily affect the feeling of trust worthiness when the product is being endorsed by a celebrity. Overall, the cumulative mean score shows an overall acceptance mean of 3.32.

Table 4: Challenges customers face in accessing the advertisements of *Indomie* noodles

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
Poor internet makes it hard to view online ads.	165	122	38	35	360	3.45	1.41	Accepted
I don't watch TV much, so I miss the ads sometimes.	32	43	105	178	360	2.12	0.10	Rejected
The ads are not shown on platforms students use often	110	128	47	75	360	3.41	1.32	Accepted
I find it hard to understand the message of some celebrity ads.	156	109	40	55	360	3.42	1.18	Accepted
Cumulative mean						3.10		Accepted

Table 4 shows the results of the 4 proportions used to evaluate the challenges faced in accessing the advertisements of *Indomie Noodles*. For the first, third and fourth propositions, the respondents accepted

that poor internet, lack of ads being shown on platforms students use, and the lack of ability to understand the messages of some celebrity ads, are the challenges faced in accessing the advertisements of *Indomie Noodles*. However, they do not find the lack of regular viewing of TV, as a challenge much, so they miss the ads sometimes. This implies that the factors hindering the success in accessing the advertisements of *Indomie Noodles*, were poor internet, lack of ads being shown on student platforms, and lack of proper understanding of messages of some celebrity ads.

Discussion of Findings

In this section, the data collected from survey on the study were discussed.

The first objective of this study was set to examine the level of exposure of PAAU students to advertisements of *Indomie Noodles* featuring celebrity endorsements. Table 1 handled this. The findings showed that majority of respondents were exposed to advertisement of *Indomie Noodles* featuring celebrity endorsement. Furthermore, the responses revealed that.

The finding supports the result of Oyeniyi and Abiodun (2019), who found that celebrity endorsements strongly affect the buying behavior of youths when it comes to noodles, especially by helping them remember the brand easily. It also agrees with Okorie and Agbaje (2017), who discovered that young people trust products more when they are promoted by celebrities they admire on social media, and this makes them more likely to buy those products.

These studies show that celebrity influence plays a big role in shaping how youths respond to advertisements, just like in the present study. The uses and gratifications theory was chosen to give backing, which explains that people choose the media they watch based on what they enjoy or need. In this case, students choose to view *Indomie* ads with celebrities because it gives them entertainment and helps them feel connected to popular culture and public figures. This makes them pay more attention to the ads and increases the chances of them liking and buying the product.

Objective number two of this study was to find out the extent to which exposure to celebrity endorsements, influences the level of patronage of *Indomie Noodles* by customers. Table 2 handled this. Findings revealed that majority agreed that seeing a celebrity in *Indomie* advertisements encourages them to want to buy the product. These findings are supported by research studies by Okorie and Aderogba (2011) who examined the role of celebrity endorsement in shaping brand preference among Nigerian consumers.

Their study found that Nigerian audiences, especially youths and students, respond well to brands endorsed by familiar public figures such as actors, musicians, and sports stars. The presence of these celebrities in advertisements created a feeling of trust and excitement among consumers, which improved both brand recall and the willingness to try the product. The findings of this is consistent with the findings of Oladimeji's (2019) work, which explained how celebrities serve as attention-grabbers in advertisements and how their personality, credibility, and appeal add value to the product.

Oladimeji emphasized that consumers often connect emotionally and psychologically with celebrities they admire, and this connection is usually passed on to the brand they endorse. These ideas are also supported by Okeke and Nwankwo (2018), who found that celebrities on social media significantly boost brand visibility and increase consumer loyalty, particularly among Nigerian youths who are very active online. The study concluded that the popularity of a celebrity, especially on platforms like Instagram and YouTube, can encourage greater customer engagement and increase buying decisions for goods like *Indomie Noodles*.

The findings are in line with the assumptions of two-step flow theory which explains how information from the media reaches audiences indirectly through opinion leaders. As, celebrities act as

opinion leaders they receive brand messages and pass them on to their followers who trust and look up to them. Because many people admire and follow celebrities on social media and television, their opinions and choices have a powerful effect on consumer behavior. When a celebrity promotes *Indomie Noodles*, their fans are more likely to see the product as desirable and reliable. Also the Agenda-Setting Theory, which suggests that the media may not always tell people what to think, but it tells them what to think about.

By consistently featuring celebrities in *Indomie* advertisements, the brand is positioned in the minds of the audience as something important or worth their attention. The repeated appearance of celebrities in *Indomie* ads influences what consumers focus on and discuss. It increases the product's visibility and helps the audience associate the brand with excitement, popularity, and quality. As a result, this steady exposure helps drive customer interest and boosts patronage.

Table 4 answered this research question. Inferences from the table indicates that celebrity advertisements had a positive influence on consumer patronage of *Indomie Noodles*. Majority of the respondents agree that seeing a celebrity influences their decisions, catches their attention, increases the likeliness to purchase the product, and increases the awareness level in noticing or remembering *Indomie Noodles* ads, implying that the involvement of celebrities played a significant role in the influence of consumer patronage of *Indomie Noodles*, although their involvement may not have been enough to directly affect their trust worthiness towards.

This suggest that while celebrity endorsements in *Indomie Noodles* ads may not have been able to influence the trustworthiness of respondents, it still had a significant influence on consumer patronage towards the product. These findings are in Line with the findings of Akinbola et al. (2014) work on, the influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer buying behaviour in Nigeria. The study focused on how Nigerian consumers, especially young adults and students, respond to celebrity endorsements. The researchers found that celebrity endorsements improved brand visibility, product appeal, and willingness to try new products. The study also found that not all consumers trust the product solely because of the celebrity figure.

The findings also fall in line with the assumptions of the theory adopted for this study states that the believability of a message depends largely on the credibility of its source, is central to understanding why celebrity endorsements may or may not influence consumer behavior fully. The theory asserts that for a message to be persuasive, the communicator (in this case, the celebrity) must be seen as credible, possessing expertise, trustworthiness, and sometimes attractiveness Asemah,(2013).

The respondents spend time watching celebrity involvements in advertisements, and this tends to affect the purchasing behavior on how they respond when watching celebrity ads on *Indomie Noodles*. Specifically, respondents accepted that involvements of celebrity on *Indomie Noodles* ads influences them on their purchasing decision, attention sustainability decision, the likeliness to purchase decision, and the noticeability, towards remembering the product, therefore celebrity involvement in ads played a role in influencing consumer patronage.

The research question 4 examine the challenges involved in accessing the advertisements of *Indomie Noodles* by respondents. The factors that hindered the success the accessing the advertisements of *Indomie Noodles* are analyzed in table 5. The table showed that factors that pose as challenges includes Poor internet, lack of ads showcase on students platforms, inability in understanding the ad messages.

Limited or unstable internet connection, makes it difficult for students to access the internet, thereby limiting their access to the celebrity endorsed ad messages online. The lack of showcase of ads of platforms students use, makes it difficult for students to view them. The unablensness to understand celebrity ad messages, makes it difficult for students to comprehend and to patronize *Indomie Noodles*. However, the respondents rejected the second proposition – “I am unable to access the advertisements of *Indomie*

Noodles because I don't watch Television much, and sometimes miss the ads" as the challenge in accessing advertisements of *Indomie Noodles* among students.

These challenges can be linked to the uses and gratifications theory and the selective exposure theory. The uses and gratifications theory explains how individuals actively choose and use media that satisfy their personal needs and desires (Katz., Blumler, Gurevitch, 1974). In this case, students prefer platforms that offer quick, entertaining, and personalized content usually on their smartphones and apps.

If *Indomie* ads do not appear on these preferred platforms, the audience will simply not engage with them. Furthermore, the selective exposure theory by Klapper, (1960) suggests that people only expose themselves to media content that aligns with their interests or beliefs. Students are more likely to engage with content that is fun, trendy, and relevant to their lifestyle. If the celebrity adverts are hard to understand, boring, or seem irrelevant, students may ignore or avoid them altogether. This explains why unclear advertising messages act as a serious challenge to ad effectiveness.

The rejection of the second proportion – "I am unable to access the advertisements of *Indomie Noodles*" suggests that television is not a significant barrier to accessing *Indomie Noodles* celebrity ads. This implies that the adverts content and message is not a primary challenge, but rather the unablensness to watch television, that limits access. The findings revealed that the major challenge in accessing celebrity ads on *Indomie Noodles*, is the frequent inability to watch television, and to this reason, they miss the ads frequently.

1. Analysis from Table 2 showed that most respondents are highly exposed to advertisements of *Indomie Noodles* featuring celebrity endorsements.
2. Inference from Table 3 indicates that (73.63%) of the respondents are influenced by celebrity endorsed and it helps to increase the level of patronage among respondents.
3. The data analyzed from Table 4 indicated that the involvement of celebrities in the advertisements has a positive influence and it enhances consumer patronage of *Indomie Noodles* with the cummulative mean of (3.93).
4. Analysis from Table 5 revealed the challenges faced in accessing the advertisements of *Indomie Noodles* among respondents with the cumulative mean of (3.08). However, the findings revealed that poor internet, lack of showage on platform respondents use, and the inability to understand to understand some celebrity ads messages pose the major challenges in accessing the advertisements of *Indomie Noodles*.
5. Analysis from table 6 outlines explanations on the various ways on how *Indomie* celebrity endorsed adverts has affected patronage of respondents with a cumulative mean of (3.90). The involvement of celebrity endorsements in ads stands out as an efficient and effective way of influencing consumer patronage.

Conclusion

Social media celebrity endorsement is an important way of influencing consumer patronage, and it has the potential to influence the way customers see and feel about *Indomie Noodles*, so as to increase the patronage level among customers. Therefore, the involvement of celebrity endorsements in social media ads, emerges as a significant measure to influence customer patronage.

It usage is able to appeal ad message to the audience, appealing to their feelings and emotions, thereby fostering massive engagement and patronage. It is used for shaping and influencing the opinion of consumer towards *Indomie Noodles* patronage. The study found that celebrity endorsements in

advertisements, plays a crucial role in influencing customers decision. The study observed that social media celebrity endorsement has a strong had a persuasive impact on viewers, significantly shaping their choice preferences. The use of these celebrities in advertisements gives a powerful and persuasive rhetoric on prompted viewers, to emotionally connect with the product, resulting in increased consumer engagement and patronage.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings;

1. Indomie should continue to collaborate with well-known, trusted, and relatable celebrities. These celebrities should reflect the values and identity of the target audience, especially students and young consumers, to deepen emotional connection and trust in the brand.
2. Indomie should increase the frequency of its advertisements. This can be achieved by consistently placing these adverts on digital platforms like Instagram, YouTube, TikTok, and WhatsApp, where the target audience is more active. Regular exposure will improve recall, brand familiarity, and likelihood of purchase.
3. Indomie should ensure that all messages are communicated in simple and clear language. Use of subtitles, local dialects, relatable storylines, and slower speech pace can make adverts more inclusive and easier to understand by a wider audience.
4. Indomie should consider alternative methods of dissemination. These may include short, low-data video formats for online use, or expanded use of traditional media like radio and television. Doing so will ensure that even people in low-connectivity areas can still engage with the adverts.

References

- Abdulwahab, T. A. (2015). *Fundamentals of research methodology in social and management sciences*. Ilorin: University Press.
- Adebayo, S., & Ajiboye, O. (2020). Consumer perception of advertising in Nigeria: A behavioral analysis. *Nigerian Journal of Marketing Research*, 8(2), 112–130.
- Adeyanju, A., & Olusola, R. (2021). The role of social media influencers in brand marketing: A Nigerian perspective. *West African Journal of Business Studies*, 14(3), 99–115.
- Adeosun, L. P. K., & Ganiyu, R. A. (2020). Influence of social media celebrity endorsement on consumers' brand preference in Lagos. *Nigerian Journal of Marketing Research*, 8(1), 1–12.
- Agbaje, O. H., & Fadipe, M. K. (2020). The effect of celebrity endorsement on customer loyalty in the Nigerian food industry. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 12(4), 33–42.
- Aina, O. A., & Ogunlade, A. A. (2017). Celebrity endorsement and brand performance: A study of Indomie noodles in Nigeria. *Journal of Marketing and Communication Studies*, 6(2), 77–89.
- Akinbode, M., & Banjo, O. (2021). Celebrity endorsement and consumer purchase behavior in Nigeria: A case study of Lagos youth. *Journal of African Marketing Studies*, 8(1), 45–58.
- Akinbola, O. A., Ojo, O. O., & Oloruntoba, A. (2014). The influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer buying behaviour in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 5(9), 178–187.

- Asemah, E. S. (2010). *Research methods and procedures in mass communication*. Jos University Press.
- Asemah, E. S., Ekharefo, D. O., & Okpanachi, R. A. (2013). *Mass media, propaganda and development: A discourse*. Jos University Press.
- Asika, N. (2016). *Research methodology in the behavioural sciences* (2nd ed.). Lagos: Longman Nigeria Plc.
- Boon, S. D., & Lomore, C. D. (2001). Admirer-celebrity relationships among young adults: Explaining perceptions of celebrity influence on identity. *Human Communication Research*, 27(3), 432–465.
- Choi, S. M., & Rifon, N. J. (2012). It is a match: The impact of congruence between celebrity image and brand on advertising effectiveness. *Journal of Advertising*, 41(2), 45–57.
- Emetumah, I.F., Okorie, A.G., Duru, N., Macaulay S.U., Nnosike E. N & Etumnu, E.W. (2022). When the digital media do the magic of effective advertising of health supplements in Owerri metropolis. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*, 16(4), 41-49. <https://doi.org/doi:10.9734/AJARR/2022/v16i430467>
- Erdogan, B. Z. (1999). Celebrity endorsement: A literature review. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 15(4), 291–314.
- Erdogan, B. Z. (2019). Celebrity endorsement: A literature review and research agenda. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 25(4), 367–390.
- Eze, R., & Madueke, C. V. (2018). Social media influence and youth buying behaviour: A study of Nigerian undergraduates. *International Journal of Media and Communication Studies*, 6(1), 12–26.
- Ezie, O. C. (2020). Influence of advertisement on consumer buying behavior among undergraduates in Enugu State. *Nigerian Journal of Communication Research*, 9(1), 102–115.
- Ezenwa, A. C., & Ohakwe, J. (2020). Celebrity endorsement and consumer trust: A Nigerian perspective. *African Journal of Marketing Management*, 12(3), 33–41.
- Ibrahim, A. M., & Salami, S. T. (2021). Social media influencers and consumer buying behavior in Nigeria: A study of fast-moving consumer goods. *African Journal of Digital Marketing*, 3(1), 102–117.
- Ibrahim, M., & Akintunde, B. (2019). The effectiveness of digital advertising on consumer purchase intentions in Nigeria. *African Journal of Business and Economic Research*, 15(2), 55–72.
- Ibok, N. I. (2013). The influence of celebrity endorsement on the buying behavior of the Nigerian youth. *International Journal of Marketing and Technology*, 3(5), 62–79.